

Coupling interior and atmospheric models

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Abstract

When constructing stellar structure models one needs to formulate appropriate inner and outer boundary conditions. For formulating the outer boundary condition, results stemming from model atmospheres are used at various levels of sophistication. I will discuss the basic procedures and involved issues when applying 1D and hydrodynamical 3D model atmospheres. Primarily asteroseismology has driven the developments towards so called patched models where the whole outer structure of an atmospheric model is coupled to an inner stellar structure model, providing overall models of perhaps highest physical fidelity.

1 Introduction

Asteroseismology is a flourishing field of astronomy. It is driven by the development of ever more stable ground-based spectrographs as well as high-precision photometric space missions. Asteroseismology holds the promise to derive stellar properties with unprecedented accuracy including even usually inaccessible interior features. To make full use of the scientific potential, accurate models are needed for the interpretation of the observational data. The stringent requirements put on stellar models to be applied in the, e.g., PLATO data analysis are consequences of this realization. One notoriously problematic region are the surface layers which limit the predictive power of stellar models in terms of oscillation frequencies. One approach to remove the so-called “surface effect” is to couple interior stellar models with models better adapted to the physics operating in the shallow layers. The way how this coupling is performed is the subject of this review.

In the framework of the standard stellar structure equations, two issues render the description of stars close to their surfaces problematic. As soon as the stellar plasma starts to become transparent, the radiative transfer becomes non-local and cannot be treated as diffusion process accurately anymore. When this happens, also the wavelength dependence of the radiative transfer cannot be treated by just using a summary, properly averaged (namely Rosseland) opacity. The other issue is related to the energy transport by convection which in cool stars is an important energy transport process in their envelopes. Due to the drop in density towards the surface the convective transport becomes inefficient and the convective layers show a markedly superadiabatic temperature profile. While for convective regions in the stellar interiors the assumption of an adiabatic temperature profile is an excellent approximation, for the modeling of the superadiabatic near-surface layers one is in need of a more detailed treatment. Since the convective energy transport is the net result of heat carried by adjacent up- and down-moving gas packets, it is an intrinsically multi-dimensional process and as such at odds with the the one-dimensional geometry assumed in standard stellar structure models. The way out was to apply mean field models rendering the convective transport an effectively one-dimensional process. Today, the most commonly applied descriptions are Mixing-Length Theory (MLT; Böhm-Vitense, 1958), and the Full Spectrum of Turbulence model (FST; Canuto & Mazzitelli, 1991). Both models contain free parameters not provided by

theory which need to be calibrated by external means.

To improve the situation, the idea now is to combine models better suited to the physics of the surface layers with models of the interiors appropriate for the conditions encountered there. In the case of the radiative transfer classical 1D model atmospheres provide the most detailed description of non-local and wavelength-dependent radiative transfer albeit restricted to one-dimensional structures. This means that the convective energy transport is based on MLT or FST with their inherent limitations. The convective energy transport problem coupled to radiation is addressed with the help of time-dependent and multi-dimensional models (short “3D models” hereafter). Since 3D models are demanding in terms of computational resources the necessary coverage of parameter space is not as complete as in the case of classical model atmospheres. However, completeness has by now reached a level that makes 3D models a viable option when one wants to build grids of combined models coupling interior and surface structures.

In the following, I start with a brief reminder of the basics of standard stellar models, and afterwards discuss the application of 1D and 3D stellar surface models in coupled – sometimes also called “patched” – stellar models. Along the way, I discuss some practical aspects of the approach largely following the historic developments.

2 1D modeling of the stellar structure – overview

Mathematically, standard models of spherically symmetric stars can be written in the form of four ordinary differential equations (ODEs) describing the runs of radius r , pressure P , luminosity L_r , and temperature T as function of the mass m_r within a given radial position (as independent variable). Other formulations are possible but here we want to stick to the given formulation for definiteness. A number of constitutive relations need to be added describing the equation-of-state of stellar matter, its opacity, the energy production, and the thermal response of stellar shells to compression or expansion. Further physics like rotation or transport processes other than of energy can be build-in. We ignore these complications in the following since they are largely decoupled from the issue of combining interior and outer structures.

The general solution of a set of four ODEs depends on four arbitrary constants. The actual solution of the stellar struc-

ture equations is selected by four boundary conditions. Commonly, one requires the two conditions $r = 0$ and $L_r = 0$ to be fulfilled at the stellar center ($m_r = 0$). Two more are needed which are less obvious to pick. Typically one wants to model a star of given total mass M_* . At the outer boundary at $m_r = M_*$ pressure and temperature have dropped dramatically with respect to their values in the central regions of a star so that the simplest conditions would be $P = 0$ and $T = 0$. This is of course very rough, and to a large part this review deals with the question how to refine the outer boundary values of P and T . For finding the solution compatible with the boundary conditions one might proceed by picking trial values of the central pressure P_c and temperature T_c and integrate the structure equations outwards trying to match the given outer conditions. While this simple scheme is in fact technically not working, it nevertheless gives a conceptual picture helping to understand the overall problem.

In the outer stellar layers typically no energy is produced, and the thermal adjustment time is short. In the further discussion I assume that a star is in complete thermal (flux-constant) and hydrostatic equilibrium as far as its surface layers are concerned. This should be an excellent approximation as long as no pulsating stars like Cepheids are considered.

3 The array of $T(\tau)$ -relations – or q -functions

The theory of stellar atmospheres suggests a generic relation between temperature and optical depth – a $T(\tau)$ -relation – of the form:

$$T^4 = \frac{3}{4} T_{\text{eff}}^4 [\tau + q(\tau)], \quad (1)$$

where T_{eff} is the effective temperature of the star and q an arbitrary function. In the case of a gray atmosphere in radiative equilibrium q is the Hopf function. τ is usually taken to be the Rosseland mean optical depth. Empirically, q is usually set by considering calibration cases, and thereafter one is relying on the scaling with T_{eff} given by Eq. (1).

Together with the hydrostatic condition and given opacity relation (1) allows one to integrate a $T(P)$ -relation. This is the approach taken in standard stellar models to calculate the structure of the optically thin layers. At some point one is switching to the equations describing the interiors. Allowing for deviations from radiative equilibrium the q -function can mimic any $T(\tau)$ relation. A structure calculated assuming the Eddington approximation for gray radiative equilibrium is a popular choice, amounting to $q(\tau) = \text{const.} = \frac{2}{3}$. Historically, other choices were taken. Below an incomplete but representative list of $T(\tau)$ relations being based on empirical constraints or theoretical models:

- Henyey *et al.* (1965): studying line blanketing and sphericity effects
- Krishna Swamy (1966): modeling the Sun, ϵ Eri, and Gmb 1830
- Baraffe *et al.* (1995): boundary conditions extracted from full-fledged PHOENIX model atmospheres for very low-mass models
- Christensen-Dalsgaard *et al.* (1996): fit to VAL-C semi-empirical solar model atmosphere, used in their solar model S
- Trampedach *et al.* (2014): q extracted from horizontally averaged 3D model atmospheres

Figure 1: Kiel diagram showing contours of constant pressure (green lines) and temperature (red lines) at fixed optical depth $\log \tau = 3$. The P/T-values were derived from a dense grid of simplistic 1D model atmospheres indicated by black dots. A solar evolutionary track taken from the PARSEC repository (Bressan *et al.*, 2012) is depicted in black.

Where should one couple outer structure based on a $T(\tau)$ -relation to the inner structure computed with the standard stellar structure equations? Also here various choices can be taken, like the depth at which convection sets in, where $T = T_{\text{eff}}$, or at a certain optical depth. In any case, typically the following conditions hold (approximately) at the fitting point since it is located close to the stellar surface

$$r \approx R_*, \quad L_r \approx L_*, \quad m_r \approx M_*. \quad (2)$$

4 Matching procedure using model atmospheres

Already early on it was realized that the scaling suggested by relation (1) is perhaps too simplistic. For instance, if a significant change in the chemical composition can lead to changes in the $T(\tau)$ -relation even at the same T_{eff} . Hence, the idea was to use 1D model atmospheres – perhaps again calibrated on the Sun or other reference object – with the hope that they give improved scaling properties.

4.1 Matching procedure – schematically

Figure 1 illustrates schematically the matching procedure between interior solution and model atmosphere. It was inspired by the description of the matching procedure given by Chabrier & Baraffe (1997). Chabrier *et al.* are dealing with low-mass (M-type) stars for which the outer boundary condition has a large impact on the overall structure (primarily radius) of the stellar model. Hence, it is not surprising that the authors took recourse to detailed model atmospheres to set the outer boundary condition.

The matching works in the way that the interior solution provides M_* , R_* , and L_* at the matching point from which effective temperature T_{eff} and gravitational acceleration $\log g$ can be computed. For given chemistry, this defines the model atmosphere that should have the same thermodynamic conditions at the matching point as the interior solution. In general, the momentum and energy balance governing the outer solution provide two functions $f_i(P, T, L_r, r) = 0$ for determining the conditions at the matching point. An iterative adjustment is usually necessary to match inner and outer solution with the desired accuracy.

4.2 Matching procedure – practical problems

Figure 2 tries to summarize practical problems that arise when it comes to the matching of inner and outer solution. When matching pressure and temperature at the fitting point this does not guarantee a smooth transition between inner and outer solution. Smoothness is a very desirable property in the context of asteroseismology to avoid artificial wave reflection. There are several reasons for non-smoothness which are not of fundamental nature but related to the actual implementation of the physical processes in the inner and outer model – as summarized below.

Chemical composition, equation-of-state, and opacities: the demands on the constitutive functions are usually quite different in stellar structure and atmospheric models. For instance, densities reached in the stellar interiors demand for the inclusion of effects of degeneracy, which is not the case in atmospheric models. In a model atmosphere opacities need to be known as a function of wavelength while for the interior model wavelength averages (Rosseland mean opacities) suffice. This leads to different ideas about their implementation, and typically results in inconsistencies.

Treatment of the convective energy transport: even if inner and outer solution are using the same MLT or FST description, care has to be exercised that the inherent free parameters (the mixing-length parameter as the most prominent one) are chosen to be the same. Otherwise the same flux – or luminosity – would be carried by a different temperature gradient.

Turbulent pressure: a rather murky area is turbulent pressure. Is it included in a model, and if so in which way? This I had in mind when putting in Fig. 2 the question: “What P is meant?”

Geometry: stellar structure models assume spherical symmetry which is not as universally the case for atmospheric models which often assume a plane-parallel geometry with depth-independent gravity. In particular when the matching point is not located very close to the surface, the inconsistency in geometry becomes an issue which needs consideration.

Figure 2: My semi-artistic attempt to illustrate the matching and its inherent problems: the inner solution (turquoise line) is fitted to the outer solution (red line) by the condition that temperature T and pressure P coincide at the matching point. However, this does not guarantee smoothness of the combined solution at the matching point.

Researchers have worked to overcome the aforementioned issues. I will show some examples in the next sections. However, efforts did not come to an end yet. A recent example of

an investigation of the influence of the outer boundary condition on stellar structure models – here for TP-AGB stars – is Wagstaff & Weiss (2018).

5 Choice of matching depth and convection model

Figure 3 (the reader should not get confused by the numbering of the figures stemming from the original paper) shows results of Montalbán *et al.* (2001) who investigated effects of the choice of the depth in which inner and outer solution are matched, as well of the choice of the convection model used in the two solutions (MLT or FST). They combined ATLAS9 model atmospheres (Kurucz, 1993; Kupka, 1996) with ATON stellar structure models (Ventura *et al.*, 1998). The upper two panels illustrate that an inconsistent choice of the convection model used in the outer ATLAS9 and inner ATON solution lead to a significant dependence of the combined solution on the location of the matching point. Moreover, one can end up with strong jumps of the temperature gradient at the matching point. This is not at all surprising, since the same flux is associated with a different temperature gradient in the two convection models.

If one chooses the same convection model (here FST) for the inner and outer solution the situation looks much more benign, and the combined structure does not sensitively depend on the depth of the matching point. This is a bit surprising for a low matching depth. At $\tau = 1$ the diffusion approximation used in the interior models is not accurate so that one would perhaps expect stronger effects than actually present. However, in the present context this insensitivity to the adopted radiative transfer description is advantageous.

Figure 4 shows an example of coupled – in this case solar – models by Vandenberg *et al.* (2008). The inner solution was computed with the Victoria stellar structure code (Vandenberg *et al.*, 2006), the outer layers taken from MARCS model atmospheres (Gustafsson *et al.*, 2008). In fact, the MARCS atmospheres were applied in an indirect way by differentially correcting and scaling the Holweger-Müller solar atmosphere (Holweger & Mueller, 1974) to other effective temperatures. For comparison, standard $T(\tau)$ -relations were also used. Two different matching depths were tested. Care was exercised to use the same chemical abundance, equation-of-state, and convection model (MLT) in the inner and outer solution. Following standard practice, the mixing-length parameter of all models was calibrated against the present Sun. Vandenberg and collaborators addressed the basic question whether the more detailed MARCS-based outer boundary condition gives a more accurate scaling of the stellar structure than standard $T(\tau)$ -relations. They compared isochrones to color-magnitude diagrams of the open cluster M67 (of about solar metallicity) and the globular cluster M68 ($[M/H] \approx -2$). While for M67 the results indicate that the coupled models indeed provide a more accurate scaling, the results for M68 remain inconclusive due to uncertainties related to the cluster’s distance, age, and reddening, as well as the applied color transformation.

Before finishing this section on coupling classical 1D atmospheres and inner structure models I want to mention the approach of Bernkopf (1998). Bernkopf used solar Balmer lines observed in solar-type stars to constrain the mixing-length parameter of his model atmospheres. He was able to simultaneously match solar radius, luminosity and profiles of Balmer lines with a coupled model in the framework of FST. He coined the term of “unified stellar models” for this kind of model. Fairly recently, Wu *et al.* (2015) followed-up on Bernkopf’s idea using a bigger sample of stars for cali-

Fig. 2. Evolutionary tracks for $0.8 M_{\odot}$ computed using: **a)** MLT atmospheres matched with an interior computed with FST at $\tau = 1, 10$ and 100 ; and **b)** FST atmospheres matched with an interior computed with FST

Fig. 3. The temperature stratification in the atmosphere and in the interior corresponding to the models at 10 Gyr ($\log L/L_{\odot} \sim 0.176$) from the tracks shown in Fig. 2. Big empty dots represent the points of junction between the interior and the atmosphere

Figure 3: Evolutionary tracks and internal structures of coupled models with differing depths of matching. The upper panels depict the situation when applying different convection models (MLT+FST) in the outer and inner solution while the lower panels illustrate a consistent treatment (FST+FST). (from Montalbán *et al.*, 2001, reproduced with permission © ESO)

Fig. 4.—Plot on the H-R diagram of evolutionary tracks for $1.0 M_{\odot}$ stellar models having $Y = 0.257578$ and the Asplund heavy-element abundances (see Tables 1 and 2) with different treatments of the atmospheric layers, as indicated. In order for each case to satisfy the solar constraint (note the location of the solar symbol), the mixing-length parameter had to be set to the specified values.

Figure 4: Evolutionary tracks of coupled solar models using different outer solutions and fitting depths. The mixing-length parameters of all models were calibrated to fit the present Sun. (from Vandenberg *et al.*, 2008, reproduced with permission by the author)

bration, and non-LTE Balmer line profiles.

6 Higher fidelity with $\langle 3D \rangle$ model atmospheres

The investigations described in the previous section were essentially looking at the mass-radius and mass-luminosity relationships predicted by the models. Frequencies of stellar oscillation modes interpreted in asteroseismology put higher demands on stellar models. Not only the entropy jump at the stellar surface which is influencing the stellar radius needs to be modeled accurately. Also the detailed thermal profile of these layers has to be represented since it sets – together with the interior solution – the size of the acoustic cavity as a function of frequency. To match present observational uncertainties of the mode frequencies relative accuracies of better than 10^{-4} are needed. In particular photometric satellite missions (MOST, COROT, Kepler, BRITE, TESS, PLATO) have driven or will continue to drive the need for models of higher accuracy.

Arguably, 3D model atmospheres provide the most accurate ab initio representations of the photospheric and sub-photospheric structure of late-type stars. For highest accuracy it appears natural to use these for the outer solution. As a first step, an appropriate averaging of the multi-dimensional and time-dependent surface structure is necessary. Typically, horizontal and time-wise averages on given geometrical depth are used. This choice preserves to first order the vertical momentum balance provided the turbulent pressure is taken into account. Figure 5 shows an early attempt of coupling an average 3D outer structure – often written “ $\langle 3D \rangle$ structure” – to an inner model for the Sun.

Figure 5 illustrates already the two main effects expected when using $\langle 3D \rangle$ models: i) turbulent naturally present in

Fig. 7. Pressure as a function of depth for an averaged 3-D model (full drawn), and for the comparison standard envelope (SEM) model (dashed). The dashed-dotted curve shows the pressure stratification of a 3-D model where the gradient of the turbulent pressure has been artificially removed from the vertical pressure balance. The upper abscissa shows the corresponding position in a complete model, in terms of the fractional radius r/R

Figure 5: Solar interior model coupled to a ⟨3D⟩ outer model. (from Rosenthal *et al.*, 1999, reproduced with permission © ESO)

3D models pressure “lifts” the outer layers with respect to a model including no turbulent pressure, and ii) horizontal fluctuations together with the highly non-linear temperature response of the opacity lead to a heating of a layer at given geometrical depth. The later process was identified and dubbed “convective back-warming” by Trampedach *et al.* (2003).

The procedure of Rosenthal *et al.* gained increasing interest due to the already mentioned demands in accuracy beyond the Sun, and the availability of grids of 3D model atmospheres for cool (FGK-type) stars. Patched models have been now used to study the surface effect on mode frequencies in several cases: Piau *et al.* (see 2014); Sono *et al.* (see 2015); Ball *et al.* (see 2016); Magic & Weiss (see 2016); Trampedach *et al.* (see 2017); Jørgensen *et al.* (see 2017).

All the aforementioned pieces of work using ⟨3D⟩ models apply the so-called post-evolutionary patching procedure: an standard evolutionary model based on a $T(\tau)$ -relation is computed until the desired stellar parameters are reached, and then the outer structure is replaced by a more detailed model. This procedure neglects potential effects of the outer solution on the evolutionary path. In a recent piece of work, Jørgensen *et al.* (2018) were using ⟨3D⟩ models for all times during the (short) evolution of a solar model to its present location in the HRD. Figure 6 shows the effect on solar p-mode frequencies (green dots vs dark blue triangles). Plotted are differences between computed and observed frequencies measured by BISON (Broomhall *et al.*, 2009; Davies *et al.*, 2014). For further comparison, the figure depicts the result for a conventional solar model (Garstec, Eddington), and effects related to the treatment of the modulation of the turbulent pressure. While the effect on the solar frequencies is mild, it is to be expected that effects grow for stars on the red giant branch. From a theoretical perspective, the continuous patching of ⟨3D⟩ models to interior solutions is the at present most accurate way the coupling of outer and inner structure can be performed.

7 Final remarks

While work is under way to establish one-dimensional stellar structure models that allow one to calculate mode frequencies with high fidelity one should not forget that there are still lingering problems for diagnosing the quality of the obtained models. Oscillation frequencies are commonly

Figure 5. Frequency difference between BISON observations and the solar models listed in Table 1. We only include radial modes ($\ell = 0$) with frequencies above $1000 \mu\text{Hz}$.

Figure 6: Frequency residuals of post-evolutionary patched models (dots) and models with on-the-fly patched outer solution (triangles). Further details see text (from Jørgensen *et al.*, 2018, reproduced following the rules of MNRAS).

computed in the adiabatic approximation. Moreover, the interaction between convection and oscillation – in particular the modulation of the turbulent pressure – is treated in a parameterized fashion, if at all. Houdek *et al.* (2017) illustrate that the different treatment can lead to frequency changes of the same order as the frequency differences emerging from models of different surface structure. Moreover, the velocity fields and thermal inhomogeneities present in the surface layers make the wave propagation in this region a genuinely multi-dimensional problem (e.g., Murawski & Roberts, 1993a,b; Zhugzhda & Stix, 1994; Rosenthal *et al.*, 1995, and follow-up works). Last but not least, the influence of magnetic fields on the stellar structure models and on mode frequencies is typically not accounted for. In my opinion, more work is needed to disentangle the various effects more cleanly. Nevertheless, the coupling of detailed surface models and interior structure models came already a long way and provide models of unprecedented fidelity.

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